

Petty Shopkeepers Opinion about Cashless India - A Study with Special Reference to Chennai City

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Mohana Priya, M., and Tamarasi Mailachalam. “Petty Shopkeepers Opinion about Cashless India - A Study with Special Reference to Chennai City.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 6-9.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3371255>

M. Mohana Priya

Ph.D. Full Time Research Scholar

Department of Commerce

Madras Christian College

East Tambaram, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

Dr. Mrs. Tamarasi Mailachalam, M.Com., M.Phil., Ph.D.,

Head, Associate Professor & Research Supervisor

Department of Commerce, Madras Christian College

Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

India aims to limit cash circulation and cash transaction which was intended to come out in the form of demonetization. The intention behind demonetization is focusing on eradicating corruption and makes each transaction accountable. The cash circulation was controlled to a larger extent and focused to bring digital payments. The shortage of bank notes during demonetization leads to start using digital wallets. Digital users easily adopted the technological banking and shift their transactions made through online. India grows very fast in making payments and made transactions digitally. The main objective of this paper is to identify the opinion of petty shopkeepers towards cashless India in Chennai City. Simple Random Sampling technique was used to select the sample respondents. The petty shopkeepers were selected as sample respondents. The study was carried out in Chennai City. 100 sample respondents were selected. Percentage Analysis, t-Test and ANOVA were used to process the data using SPSS to identify the opinion of petty shopkeepers about cashless India. This paper has discussed about the opinion of petty shopkeepers about cashless India in Chennai City.

Keywords: Cashless Economy, Digital Payments, Petty Shopkeepers, Demonetization.

Introduction

India aims to limit cash circulation and cash transaction which was intended to come out in the form of demonetization. The intention behind demonetization is focusing on eradicating corruption and makes each transaction accountable. The cash circulation was controlled to a larger extent and focused to bring digital payments. The shortage of banknotes during demonetization leads to start using digital wallets. Digital users easily adopted the technological banking and shift their transactions made through online. India grows very fast in making payments and made transactions digitally. The below picture clearly draft the usage of cashless focused within a year after demonetization.

	Cards at PoS	IMPS	UPI	USSD	PPI
Value (₹ crore)					
September 2017	45,194	71,760	5,293	32.36	2,759.6
August	45,708	65,149	4,127	29.42	2,722.2
Change (%)	-1.12	10.15	28.26	9.99	1.37
Volume (million)					
September	229.18	82.85	30.78	0.2	87.46
August	243	75.7	16.6	0.2	89.7
Change (in %)	-5.67	9.5	85.31	5.26	-2.5

Data for card transactions is sourced from four banks and that for PPI transactions from eight non-bank issuers
Source: RBI

Going Cashless

A central bank-appointed panel wants to wean India off cash

■ Number of digital transactions per capita (per year)

*India's data is for March 2019, while for other countries, the figures are for 2017.

Source: Report of India's High Level Committee on Deepening of Digital Payments

BloombergOpinion

India positions the 10th rank among countries in the world using Digital Payments. India attains this position in a short span of time after demonetization and focused on cashless economy. But on the negative side people who don't know how to make digital payments are facing lot of problems. The opinion of every person is different in going towards cashless economy in India. This study was focused on the petty shopkeepers' opinion about cashless India.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this paper is to identify the opinion of petty shopkeepers towards cashless India in Chennai City

Methodology

Simple Random Sampling technique was used to select the sample respondents. The petty shopkeepers were selected as sample respondents. The study was carried out in Chennai City. 100 sample respondents were selected. Percentage Analysis, t-Test and ANOVA were used to process the data using SPSS to identify the opinion of petty shopkeepers about cashless India.

Findings and Discussion

The data collected were analysed and presented below:

The major findings of the demographic profile of the sample respondents in this study are

- Equal weightage is given to both the gender. 50 per cent male and 50 per cent female respondents were selected for the study.
- Majority are in the age group of 41-50 years (68 per cent).
- Majority are having owned petty shop at their house or nearer to house (90 per cent).
- Majority of 81 per cent of the respondents were completed only upto 5th to 8th Standard.
- Majority of the respondents are running family business (49 per cent).
- Majority of 92 per cent of the respondents prefer to use cash as payment mode.
- Majority of 80 per cent of the respondents preferred to save money in bank and preferred debit card to assess their account for making their transactions.

Hypothesis Testing -1 (t-Test)

Ho: There is no significant difference between male and female with respect to opinion towards Cashless India

Gender	Mean	S.D	F	p-value
Male	57.43	3.75	0.710	0.001*
Female	53.54	3.59		

Source: Primary Data

Since p-value is lesser than 0.01 the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 % level of significance. There is significant difference between male and female with respect to opinion towards cashless India. It shows that male and female are having different perception and opinion about Cashless India.

Hypothesis Testing -2 (ANOVA)

Ho: There is no significant difference between age group of the respondents with respect to opinion about cashless India.

Age in Years	Mean	S.D	F	p-value
Upto 30	54.4494	4.72585	0.670	0.004**
31-40	59.2946	5.41755		
41-50	57.2526	5.14223		
Above 50	57.5445	4.54431		

Source: Primary Data

Since p-value is lesser than 0.01 the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 % level of significance. There is significant difference between age group of the respondents with respect to opinion towards cashless India. It shows that age plays a vital role in adopting cashless economy. The customers are hesitating with going to Cashless transactions due to fear about cyber issues and they prefer to go with cash transactions due to various reason. One among important factor is their wholesalers and retailers are giving stock prefer cash payments and also they are unaware of maintaining proper accounts.

Conclusion

Cashless India helps to fight against terrorism, corruption, money laundering but one biggest problem in the working of cashless economy in India is cybercrime and anxiety about using digital payment systems. Most of the petty shopkeepers are not technically and digitally literate to go with cashless economy. For smooth implementation of cash less system in India, the following

measures are recommended. Government have to bring transparency and efficiency in e-payment system, strategies used by government and RBI to encourage cashless transactions by licensing payment banks, promoting mobile wallets and withdrawing service charge on cards and digital payments. A financial literacy campaign should be conducted by government time to time to make population aware of benefits of electronic payments.

References

1. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/banking/finance/view-cashless-india-could-be-a-model-for-the-world/articleshow/69669960.cms>.
2. <https://www.financialexpress.com/industry/cashless-payments-india-embraces-upi-growth-shoots-up-85-pct/884144/>
3. <https://www.livemint.com/industry/banking/cashless-india-could-be-a-model-for-the-world-1559790271860.html>.
4. <https://yourstory.com/2018/03/increasing-digital-payments-equip-indias-cashless-vision>
5. Humphrey, D. B. (2004). —Replacement of cash by cards in U.S. Consumer Payments, *Journal of Economics and Business*, 56, 211–225.
6. Lee, Jinkook, Fahzy Abdul-Rahman, and Hyungsoo Kim. “Debit card usage: an examination of its impact on household debt.” *Financial Services Review*. 16.1 (2007): 73.
7. More wedge, C. K., Holtzman, L., & Epley, N. (2007). Unfixed resources: perceived costs, consumption, and the accessible account effect. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 34(4), 459–467).
8. Moses-Ashike, H. (2011), —Cashless Economic can Reduce Risk of Carrying Huge Cash, [Online] Available: <http://www.businessdayonline.com/.../22217>.
9. Odior, E.S., and Banuso, F.B. (2012): Cashless Banking in Nigeria: Challenges, Benefits & Policy Implications. *European Scientific Journal*. Vol 8, pp. 12 – 16.
10. Roth, B. L. (2010).—The Future of Money: The Cashless Economy – Part 1. [Online] Available: <https://www.x.com/.../futuremoney-cashless-economy—part-i>.
11. Woodford M. (2003). —Interest & Price: Foundation of a Theory of Monetary Policy, Princeton University Press.